

A STYLISTIC ANALYSIS REPETITION IN ERNEST HEMINGWAY'S WORKS

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Annotation. In this article, looking at the work of Hemingway's life, his works were drawn to the analysis. Examples of the opinions of linguists who conducted research on his works are presented.

Key words: Hemingway, repetition, work, "The Oldman and The Sea".

Ernest Hemingway (pronounced: Ernest Hemingway; 1899.21.7, OakPark, near Chicago - 1961.2.7, Ketcham, Idaho) is an American writer. Journalist in Kansas City since 1917 quality of work as a reporter. A participant in the First World War (1914-18), Hemingway lived in Paris until 1928, and in Cuba in 1939-60. "In our time" (1924). The stories "The Sun Rises" (1926, titled "Fiesta" in English), "A Farewell to Arms!" (1929), "The Horn of the Ox", "Francis Macomber's Happiness", "The Snows of Kilimanjaro" (1936), "Fatigue and Deprivation" (1937), short story collections such as "Afternoon Death" (1932), "Green Hills of Africa" (1935), "No Flag to the Winner" (1933).

He is the author of the highly artistic novel "On the banks of the river, in the shade of trees" (1950), and the short story "The old man and the sea" (1952). Especially "Farewell gun!" The novel is an incomparable logic war, human rights, violation of free will, and at the same time, human courage, dignity and the superiority of love over all evil forces are expressed.

The story "the old man and the sea" (1952) brought Hemingway great fame. Hemingway created a characteristic style based on the strict impartiality inherent in him in the 20th century, which later writers who grew up from the American continent often resorted to.

"The stylistic potential of the idiolect of Ernest Hemingway in the novel "The Old Man and The Sea" is remarkably noticed in the use of repetitions in various functions. Repetitions are directly related to the "style-forming core" of Ernest Hemingway's individual handwriting. They stem from the nature of the creative individuality of the writer. In the nature of repetitions, in their quantitative use, in the nature and stylistic originality, the emotion, tension of the narration are manifested with particular

brightness. The origins of the repetition in the excitement accompanying the expression of a feeling brought to the highest tension.” [2]

“The Old Man and the Sea”. There are 10 definite articles and only one indefinite article among 80 words contained in the second paragraph. The whole story contains 84,1% of definite articles and only 15,9% of indefinite ones whereas usually article ratio is 60-70% - 30-40%.

The same aim is reached by initial using of the third person pronouns, which are used before names. An unknown character or object is perceived as if it had been already mentioned. “The Old Man and the Sea” begins with: “He was an old man who fished alone...” while the old man’s name – Santiago - appears only at the fourth paragraph. The same can be said about the boy and his name (Manolin). By the way Hemingway uses “Santiago” only three times and “the old man” 202 times in the narrative; Manolin – 2 times and “the boy” – 96 times. Such frequency can be explained by using the third person pronouns in the remarks for dialogues. The subject is expressed by the pronoun in 60% of the remarks.

Locative prepositions and adverbs also fulfill a stylistic function. They are about 10% of the text and they are utilized as concentrated groups in one phrase: “The boy was back now with the sardines and the two baits wrapped in a newspaper and they went down the trail to the skiff, feeling the pebbled sand under their feet, and lifted the skiff and slid her into the water.”

Sometimes Hemingway combines polysyndeton and frequent usage of prepositions in one sentence: “He no longer dreamed of storms, nor of women, nor of great occurrences, nor of great fish, nor fights, nor contests of strength, nor of his wife.”. [1]

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